

RHEOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS OF PC/MWNT COMPOSITES

M. Shin¹, J. Seo¹, S. Kim¹, S. Kim^{1*}, Y. Yoo²

¹Seoul National University of Science & Technology, Seoul, Korea

²Korea Institute of Machinery & Materials, Daejeon, Republic of Korea

*Corresponding author (sunkkim@seoultech.ac.kr)

Keywords: *nanocomposites, MWNT, carbon nanotube, melt flow index, viscosity*

MWNT (carbon nanotube) is versatile filler for the thermoplastic polymers. Since it bears favorable mechanical and electrical properties, its compounding and characterization are getting important. Polycarbonate is a multi-purpose engineering plastic with many applications. Thus, enhancing and controlling its properties by adding MWNT to it are of great importance. This work compares the rheological properties of PC/MWNT composites and virgin PC through the measurement of MFI (melt flow index) and shear rate-dependent viscosity.

1 Introduction

MWNT (carbon nanotube) is versatile filler for the thermoplastic polymers. Since it bears favorable mechanical and electrical properties, its compounding and characterization are getting important [1-5]. Polycarbonate is a multi-purpose engineering plastic with many applications. Thus, enhancing and controlling its properties by adding MWNT are of great importance. The compounding technique is well-described in [6]. This work compares the rheological properties of PC/MWNT composites and virgin PC through the measurement of MFI (melt flow index) and shear rate-dependent viscosity.

2 Experimental

To characterize the rheological properties, especially viscosities, of PC and PC/MWNT composites, a set of experiments have been prepared. In this work, the viscosities at low shear rate are evaluated with MFI measurement while the high shear viscosities are measured with a capillary rheometer.

2.1 Materials

The polymer matrix used for the measurement of the rheological properties is polycarbonate (PC TRIEX 3022IR from Samyang) combined with 5% MWNT. The neat resin and the composite are shown in Fig. 1

(a) and (b), respectively, which are all pelletized. The composite is dark black owing to the MWNT addition.

2.2 Melt Flow Index

According to ASTM 1238, MFI was measured using Melt Indexer (Tinius Olsen, MP987) at 300°C extrusion temperature with a weight of 1.2kg, which is shown in Fig. 2.

2.3 Cross-WLF viscosity model

Capillary rheometer Goettfert RG25, which is shown in Fig. 3, was used for the viscosity measurement. Diameter of employed dye was 1mm with the length of 10mm and 30mm respectively. Applied extrusion temperature was 295°C, 305°C, and 315°C.

Fig. 1 (a) Neat PC and (b) PC/MWNT 5% composites.

Fig. 2 Melt indexer (Tinius Olsen, MP987).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Melt Flow Index

MFI of PC was 14g/10min and that of PC/MWNT was 2.62g/10min, 5.3 times lower. Fluidity of PC/MWNT composites was observed inferior to that of PC and viscosity at low shear rate is expected to be higher. We can roughly calculate the apparent viscosity based on the MFI measurement. The apparent viscosity of neat PC was 1590 Pa*s and that of the PC/MWNT composite was 2310Pa*s.

Fig. 3 Capillary rheometer (RG25, Goeffert).

3.2 Cross-WLF viscosity model

Viscosity is a very important factor of the fluid characteristics indicating the resistance to the deformation.

Viscosity is measured as the ratio of shear stress (τ) and shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) as in Equation (1). A thermoplastic polymer melt shows non-Newtonian flow. Its viscosity is expressed with Cross-WLF model, which is of the form [7]

$$\eta = \frac{\eta_o(T)}{1 + \left(\frac{\eta_o(T)\dot{\gamma}}{\tau^*} \right)^{1-n}} \quad (1)$$

where η is a viscosity, T is temperature and τ^* is the pseudo-shear stress at the end of first Newtonian regime. Moreover, for a given melt temperature, T , and the glass temperature T^* , the zero-shear viscosity, η_o , is which is expressed as

$$\eta_o = D_1 \exp \left[\frac{-A_1(T - T^*)}{A_2 + (T - T^*)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where the coefficients are in Table 1 and 2. As shown in Figure 1, viscosity decline rate of PC at high shear rate is less steep than that of PC/MWNT. As a result, the viscosity of the composite in high shear regime is higher than that of the virgin PC. This is attributed to the lubrication effect by the MWNTs. Similar effect by the MWNT is investigated in [8]. MFI measurement has revealed the better fluidity for PC/MWNT composite while the viscosity measurement has shown the opposite. Based on these results, it is expected that the viscosity reversal takes place somewhere in low shear rate regime.

4 Conclusions

This work presents measured melt flow indices and viscosities of PC/MWNT composites and virgin PC. The composite has shown lower fluidity near first Newtonian regime while lower viscosity at high shear rate regime.

Acknowledgements

This project is conducted through “The Development of Large Scale Micro-Machining

system technology”, funded by the Ministry of Knowledge Economy.

References

- [1] C Goze, L. Vaccarini, I. Henrard, P. Bernier, E Hernandez, and A. Rubio, "Elastic and Mechanical Properties of Carbon Nanotubes," Syntetic Metals, Vol.25, 2000, pp. 2500-2501.
- [2] S Roche, "Carbon Nanotubes : Exceptional Mechanical and Electrical Properties," Ann.Chim. Mat., Vol. 25, 2000, pp. 529-532.
- [3] E. T. Thostenson, Z. Ren, and T. W. Chou, Compos. Sci. Technol., 61, 1889 (2001).
- [4] C. A. Cooper, D. Ravich, D. Lips, J. Mayer, and H. D. Wagner, Compos. Sci. Technol., 62, 1105 (2002).
- [5] H. Lee, P. Fasulo, W. Rodgers, D. Paul, TPO based nanocomposites. Part 1. Morphology and mechanical properties, Polymer 46 (2005) 11673–11689.
- [6] T. Wu, E. Chen, Y. Lin, M. Chiang, G. Chang, Preparation and Characterization of Melt-Processed Polycarbonate/Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube Composites, Polymer Engineering and Science, 48(7) 1369-1375, 2008
- [7] J.D.Ferry "Viscoelastic properties of polymer," John Wiley& Sons. Inc., pp. 280-290, 1980.
- [8] S. Jain, J. Goossens, G. Peters, M. Duin and P. Lemstra, Soft Matter, 4, 1848 (2008)

PC	PC/MWNT 5%
n = 0.269	n=0.615
Tau*= 572950	Tau*=2270
D1= 5.55e+13	D1=8.50e+10
D2= 416.15	D2=411.15
D3= 0	D3=0
A1= 33.915	A1=23.827
A2= 50.8	A2=49.4

Fig. 4 Measured viscosity for PC and PC/MWNT 5% 295° C, 305C° , 315C°

Table 1. Viscosity coefficients for neat PC

295°C		305°C		315°C	
η	513Pas	η	320 Pas	η	252 Pas
T	295°C	T	305°C	T	315°C
T^*	143°C	T^*	143°C	T^*	143°C

Table 2. Viscosity coefficients for PC/MWNT 5%

295°C		305°C		315°C	
η	1142	η	882	η	687
T	295°C	T	305°C	T	315°C
T^*	138°C	T^*	138°C	T^*	138°C

Table 3. Viscosity coefficients for Corss-WLF model